

Archaeo-Serengeti Shall not Die! Threats and Prospects for the Protection of Archaeological Heritage

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Abstract

The Serengeti National Park's iconic savannahs attract almost 500,000 tourists annually. However, the general understanding of the park, does not include its archaeological heritage. For several decades, the Serengeti has been largely overlooked by archaeologists. This has led to a limited understanding among the National Park management board regarding the threats to the archaeological heritage. A reconnaissance in August 2024 revealed a number of factors that threaten the archaeological heritage within the park. Rock art is increasingly accessible to tourists without any regulation, resulting in degradation, while the installation of concrete information pedestals in rockshelter deposits at certain sites is disrupting the archaeological stratigraphy. The construction of new hotel facilities occurs without archaeological supervision, resulting in the irreversible loss of information about ancient settlements at key locations within the landscape. The recent developments have resulted in the creation of deceptive archaeological sites, attributed to the exportation of construction materials such as sand and gravel from outside the park, which are accompanied by artifacts.

Introduction

Serengeti National Park, is one of the oldest and most iconic nature reserves in the world. As part of the largest protected area on our globe, it is a priceless world heritage site. As early as the early 20th century, the area was protected as a game reserve, which had far-reaching social and ecological consequences (Sinclair and Arcese 1995). The local population, including the pastoralist Maasai and the hunter-gatherer groups commonly referred to as the Wandorobo, were displaced - often under dramatic conditions associated with a cattle pandemic (rinderpest) and famine. The decisions of the then colonial administration of British Tanganyika are controversial today and are still criticised by some quarters (Neumann 1995). In 1981, the Serengeti was inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List as a biosphere reserve. The Serengeti, as a key part of the global network of protected areas, serves as both a treasure trove of African wildlife and a significant focus point in debates about human-landscape relations. The park is administered by the Tanzania National Parks (TANAPA).

Official statistics indicate that around 500,000 tourists annually visit Serengeti National Park (<https://ticgl.com/tanzanias-tourism-booms-with-12-4-growth-contributing-17-2-to-gdp> access 2025.07.07). Numerous vehicles cross its roads daily, and many visitors stay in camps, hotels, or lodges - often promoted as luxurious. This development benefits the tourism sector,

nonetheless, the challenges of harmonizing the expanding tourist infrastructure with the park's primary objective of biosphere conservation must not be overlooked.

The Serengeti possesses not just breathtaking landscapes and wildlife, but also a rich and diverse cultural and archaeological heritage (Bower 1977; Bower and Gogan-Porter 1981). Elements such as gong rocks, rock shelters adorned ancient community paintings, and archaeological sites are frequently utilized as supplemental attractions in modern tourism offerings (Serengeti NP GMP). However, their real value extends far beyond their aesthetic use. They provide significant repositories of information regarding the prehistory and pre-colonial history of the area.

Unlike the nearby Olduvai Gorge - a world centre for hominin biocultural evolution, archaeological research in the Serengeti has been limited and sporadic. The only long-term initiative was the collaboration between the late Prof. John Bower of the University of Iowa and Prof. Audax Mabulla of the University of Dar es Salaam, which lasted from the 1970s until 2005. No archaeological research has been carried out in the park since that time. Unfortunately, this results in inadequate protection for the sites, as shown by our survey, which reveals they are frequently unwittingly destroyed due to the increase of tourism infrastructure (also see Fisher and Thompson 2005; Mabulla and Bower 2010).

The purpose of this paper is to underscore the need for the resumption of archaeological research in the Serengeti National Park. Their revitalisation will not only enhance heritage conservation, but also enrich the narratives about the character of this unique area, imparting new significance as a biocenosis that has remained unaltered by prehistoric human settlements, both hunter-gatherers (MSA/LSA) and agricultural (Pastoral Neolithic, Bantu) groups. The latter appears especially important for contemporary analyses of human impacts on the park's ecosystem (Sinclair *et al.* 2015).

“Unearthing Pan-African Crossroads” Project

In April 2023, civil war erupted in Sudan, rendering the continuation of research funded by the Polish National Science Centre in the Middle Nile Valley impossible. Project director Dr. Piotr Osypiński decided to reallocate the funds intended for the final excavation season in Sudan to preliminary research in the Serengeti National Park, while simultaneously applying for a new research grant specifically allocated for this region. In August 2024, we conducted a two-week field reconnaissance as part of P. Osypiński and A. Mabulla initiatives to relocate the sites recorded by Bower, determine their status, and identify prospects for further research, thereby enhancing our comprehension of the prehistory of the park.

John Bower and his team, with whom Audax Mabulla collaborated as a principal partner from the outset, conducted both non-invasive archaeological surveys and excavation research at several sites in the Serengeti (Bower 1977; Bower and Gogan-Porter 1981). The published reports reveal the existence of 21 sites of diverse chronology, situated in various locations inside the park; however, the provided geographical coordinates were imprecise and sometimes misleading. One MSA site (HcJd1/Loiyangalani) and three settlements linked to Pastoral Neolithic (HbJd1/SWRI, HbJd3/Wildlife Lodge, HcJe1/Gol Kopjes) were excavated (Bower 1973; Bower *et al.* 1979; Bower and Chadderdon 1986; Bower 1991). In 2024, we explored most of these sites, except Gol Kopjes (Figure 1). Relocating these sites was challenging as they are not marked anywhere within the park, available georeferences also appeared useless.

The relocation of these sites was solely due to the exceptional memory of Prof A. Mabulla and Dr F. Masele.

Figure 1 – General map of Serengeti NP and archaeological sites surveyed in 2024 (P.Osypiński, P.Wiktorowicz).

HcJd1 – example of the sites erosion and threads

The first case is the Loiyangalani site, which is the only MSA site discovered in the area. Bower's team conducted research that involved the examination of small 1sqm units, occasionally positioned adjacent to each other to form larger aggregate blocks (Bower *et al.* 2012). From 2003 to 2005, all stone artifacts and bone remains were recorded in three-dimensions (using Total Station) within an autonomous coordinate system. A definitive reference point from this period could not be currently found. However, in 2024 we located two old trenches, which facilitated the reconstruction of the original reference grid (Figure 2). A

notable environmental observation is the significant shift in the extent of the watercourse, which now almost touches the former test pits. The water table is notably elevated. This indicates that tourist traffic at the site initially (see Fisher and Thompson 2005) and later animals visiting the waterhole at this location have contributed to the erosion of several centimetres of topsoil. The original stratigraphic record of the site revealed four general levels, with the upper two levels being nearly absent (eroded) in the site where the highest concentration of artefacts was recorded. The main sedimentary horizon, characterized by a high concentration of MSA artefacts, is located just beneath the present surface. This positioning suggest a favorable prognosis for future exploration.

Figure 2 – HcJd1 map (after Bower *et al.* 2012) and georeferenced drone photo (F. Osypiński, P. Wiktorowicz) with elements of previous research (till 2005) marked in red. Inset photo: sampling OSL in the baulk of N64E72 reopened trench (M. Osypińska).

The situation improve significantly a dozen metres further south, where the backfilled trench N64E72 excavated in 2004, was relocated and successfully exposed. In the profiles, we reconstructed the original recorded stratification system and collected a series of soil samples at 10 cm-intervals, along with 5 samples for OSL dating (Figure 2 inset photo). The analyses of these samples will enhance the understanding of soil-forming processes and their absolute chronology, which is crucial for dating MSA settlements. This episode is currently dated to circa 65 Ka, based on a single OSL date, while, the ostrich egg fragments recorded within MSA-artifacts horizon have been radiocarbon dated to 13 Ka (after Masele 2017: Table 3.1). The HcJd1 site is a critical component in understanding the late phase of the MSA in East Africa and undisputedly requires further research. In early 2026, a new project funded by the Polish National Science Centre will commence, aiming to enhance the understanding of formation, absolute chronology, and context of Serengeti MSA sites.

The HcJd1 site, known as Loiyangalani, is located along the bank of a watercourse identified on maps as Ngoyongalani, which flows into the Mbalageti River. Surface investigations along the Mbalageti River have revealed additional exposures of MSA material, indicating that the entire park area, especially around Makati Lake, requires further investigations. A substantial

tourist lodge is currently under construction on the adjacent hill, providing a view of the Loiyangalani site, Makati Lake, and the surrounding plains. This area was significant for habitation during the MSA and LSA periods. The increase in tourist vehicle activities associated with the lodge will adversely impact the archaeological record of the region. Therefore, our future research in the Serengeti will focus on this area. The presence of a Heritage Impact Assessment (HIA) before construction and archaeological watching briefs during construction remain uncertain; however, it is probable that neither was conducted (see [Mabulla and Bower 2010](#)). The TANAPA Board and relevant authorities that approve the construction of tourist camps, lodges, and hotels in the Serengeti landscape demonstrate a lack of understanding of the occurrences of archaeological sites and their importance to comprehend early human settlements and the dynamics between humans, wildlife, and the environment in the Serengeti. The lack of archaeologists in TANAPA-managed parks (Mabulla and Bower, 2010) and the absence of prehistoric settlement maps contribute to this situation.

HbJd3 – issues of the rock art in Serengeti

The HbJd3/Seronera Wildlife Lodge site illustrates the importance of conducting HIA prior to construction and engaging archaeologists throughout the construction process of the lodge. In 1973, Professor John Bower conducted HIA before construction and excavations to rescue archaeological materials that would have been negatively impacted by the construction ([Bower 1973](#)). The 4-star lodge continues to operate and showcases granite rock walls that replicate prehistoric paintings of animals and humans ([Figure 3](#)). Some of the paintings are subtly discernible, offering viewers a chance for self-discovery and appreciation of the region's uniqueness approximately 5,000 years ago.

Figure 3 - Rock art imitating ancient paintings at Seronera Wildlife Lodge and actual depictions from HbJd3 recorded by Bower 1976, fig.1.

Bower's publication provide a brief description of "rock art", characterizing it as consisting of sparse and unattractive images of shields and geometric elements that are nearly contemporaneous in the region (Bower 1973:83; Bower 1976). Nevertheless, the engagement of archaeologists and the recognition of the preserved Seronera Lodge archaeological heritage have become notable tourist attractions over the past half century!

Two additional examples of TANAPA's use of archaeological heritage pertain to the rock painting sites. The first site is located next to the Ranger's post in the Moru Kopjes (HdJd2), where tourists are briefed on the rhino population monitoring program and can utilize restroom facilities without the risk of animal encounters. A painting panel depicting a large eland, accompanied by several smaller figures such as giraffes, ostriches or humans, is located directly behind the educational building. This site simply replicates prehistoric paintings that, according to rangers, were created only a few few years ago to increase tourist visitation at the ranger post. The panel's accessibility has been improved by the construction of concrete steps, and a brick plinth; and an information board has been installed next to the panel. HcJd4, a larger shelter that Bower first described and which exemplifies Maasai settlement before the establishment of the National Park has been similarly adapted for tourism. The specifics regarding the adaptation of these sites for public visitation remain unclear (Serengeti NP GMP: 17); this process likely occurred without the involvement or supervision of archaeologists. Without suitable archaeological guidance, rock paintings are at risk of degradation due to visitor interactions.

Nanyuki Lodge - false sites

An additional example of interaction with archaeological heritage observed in the Serengeti is the creation of deceptive archaeological sites. The construction of new buildings and the creation of spaces within hotels, lodges, and camps involve ground disturbances and the utilization of materials such as sand, gravel, stones sourced externally from the park. Our research indicated the presence of archaeological materials in the vicinity of the Nanyuki River lodge. Our surveys of the various kopjes surrounding the lodge revealed sparse distributions of stone artifacts. However, we observed dense scatters of stone artifacts on the surface in an area where sand had been accumulated during construction activities (Figure 4). The sand was identified as river sediments. The origin of the sand and artifacts remains unspecified; officially, the extraction of sand and aggregates is strictly prohibited within the park. These activities not only caused significant disruption to the landscape and ecosystem, but were also carried out without the involvement of archaeologists.

Figure 4 – The walking path in Nanyuki Lodge and MSA/LSA lithics redeposited within the gravel (M. Osypińska)

Conclusion

This paper aimed to present a systematic approach to the conservation and management of archaeological heritage within Serengeti National Park. The park should collaborate with archaeologists to conserve and manage its archaeological heritage. Therefore, it is essential to employ archaeologists and appoint a permanent consultant for the archaeological heritage of the Serengeti National Park, and to initiate a reconnaissance study to map archaeological sites. Our first quick survey indicates significant potential in the area, encompassing MSA, LSA, rock painting sites, and sites associated with pastoral communities. Current research projects, two of which are supported by the National Science Centre, Poland starting in 2026, present significant opportunities to initiate this endeavor. The indirect objective of these projects is to conduct surface surveys in areas that extend beyond the excavated sites. Utilizing topographic maps from the Department of Geography (Cartographic Unit) at the University of Dar es-Salaam and satellite imagery, comprehensive maps of human settlement across all prehistoric

and historic periods will be developed. The maps will serve as valuable resource for managing spaces and elements of cultural and archaeological heritage by the Park Board and the consulting professional archaeologist.

We do not intend to interfere with the management of the Serengeti National Park; however, we acknowledge the negative impacts of tourist infrastructure constructions such as hotels, lodges, camps, and roads in ecologically, archaeologically, and culturally sensitive areas ecosystem (see [Mwankunda 2024](#)). These activities represent missed opportunities to discover potential archaeological sites, as numerous lodges, hotels and camps are located in areas conducive to prehistoric settlement, exemplified by the Seronera Wildlife Lodge.

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